

CREDIT-MODULE SYSTEM, ITS BASIC PRINCIPLES AND FEATURES

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Annotation. This article examines the features of the introduction of credit-module system in higher education on the basis of the experience of advanced foreign countries in improving the quality of Education, which is an important factor for the training of highly qualified, competitive and mature personnel meeting the requirements of international standards in the institutions of Higher Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Keywords: Credit-hour system, USCS, ECTS, University Credit Transfer System, use, THE.

In the second half of the XX century, scientific and technical progress reached its highest peaks. The current level of scientific technical development (ITT) is such that the achieved rates of Science Technical and technological development can not be ensured in a separately acquired country no matter how developed the country. The next variant of ITT can be carried out only as a result of the integration of research work in the cooperation of scientists and specialists from different countries. Taking into account the fact that the development of Science Technology and technology is closely related to the level of educational development, the priority of international integration in the field of education becomes an obvious problem. This determines the relevance of the creation and application of credit technology. Because the international integration in the field of education primarily relies on the organization of the educational process on credit technology. However, we must first give a little insight about what will be discussed. Francis Bacon, a famous philosopher of the Middle Ages, advised: before starting a discussion, it is necessary to clarify the terminology for any discussion of any issue. Therefore, to correctly understand it, it is necessary to clarify in advance the basic terms used. Taking into account the inconsistencies in the translated literature and in a number of international projects carried out in the republic within the framework of the national program of Personnel Training, as a real material, we give the conditions given in the following order.

The credit system of education (credit-hours system) is aimed at Independent Education, and on the basis of individuality determines the creative mastering of knowledge, the choice of the educational path with a strict definition of the educational process and the volume of knowledge in the case of credit. Credit (Credit, Credit-hour) is a specific unit that measures the volume of educational work of a student (teacher) in accordance with the labor load in the entire academic period. One of the peculiarities of the generally accepted education in credit technology is its compliance with international general education standards and the problems of receiving documents on education, universal education program taking into account world trends, academic

freedom and educational programs variability. Students will have the opportunity to freely enter the university education level of foreign countries, Bachelor's and master's graduates will all have the right to employment in the state.

Credit-module sitemaps have come into existence in the US for the first time. In 1869, the president of Harvard University Charles Eliot introduced the concept of "credit-systems" and in 1870-80 the system of measuring the volume of Educational Sciences in credit was introduced. In order to reach a certain level, it is necessary to collect zacet units, that is, the volume of "credit-modules". On the American site USCS (US Credit system) credit-module is a measure based on the time of training.

1 credit-module is equal to the academic hours of the student's auditroiy work within a week during the semester. In June 1999, the ministers of education of 29 European countries put their hands on the Bolonsky declaration, in which the main emphasis was on the universal application of ECTS and diplomas. Currently, all European countries have been transferred to the educational loan and introduced into 1062 higher education institutions. In this way, Europe has equated the scale of assessment in the national system on the all-European template, which is a logical ECTS sitemap. According to this system, each student must collect 60 European credits in one academic year. In addition to the European, American and British credit system (zacet unit), UCTS (University Credit Transfer System) is a university credit transfer system for Asia-Pacific regions. Japan and China were not included in this USTS. The basis of the Japanese site of the zacet unit is the American system of USCS, which, in contrast, replaced the term "credit-module" with the term "zacet unit" (units).

It is estimated that ECTS credits are understood as a general educational load for each educational science, hours of communication as working hours. The ECTS sitemap is a self-recognising tool that serves to bring together a wide variety of education systems, taking into account the multinational European traditions. Therefore, in the CIS countries, the American credit system was used to ensure a solid foundation for the integration of World educational processes and a high quality of Education. An ECTS credit provides 24-36 working hours, which includes all types of communication sessions. One academic year to the ECTS system corresponds to 60 credits, 30 credits - semester.

Issuance of loans. Since the Bologna declaration, many countries have made amendments to the laws on higher education, systems that are compatible with ECTS or ECTS have often become a central element of national reforms. Austria, France, Germany, Italy, Vengria, Slovakia and other countries have linked the introduction of two phases into the education system simultaneously with the introduction of a mandatory ECTS system. Other countries, it belongs to Northern Europe, it has a traditional National Credit System, which basically corresponds to ECTS, and in some countries these two systems live together today. Denmark and Norway decided to replace their national systems with ECTS. Even in countries where there is no obligation to use loans, for example in Bulgaria, the Czech Republic, Poland or Slovenia, many universities now use ECTS to transfer loans.

The use of ECTS for the transfer of credits includes Greece and Sweden (80%), Finland and Poland (81,5%), Austria and Belgium (84%), Romania (87%), Norway (90%), Ireland and Denmark (wide). 93%). Other systems were adopted in the UK (45,5%) and in Turkey (58%). In some countries, relatively many do not use ECTS or other systems, for example, Portugalaliyada (34%), Bulgaria (38 5%) and Venice (44%). Approximately 75 percent of universities in the countries of Southeast Europe (Sotho) have still not introduced ECTS as a credit transfer system.

Collection of credits. The idea of using ECTS as a system of accumulation not only for those who plan to study abroad (mobile students), but also for all students, is devoted to the use of loans in the Bologna declaration in terms of lifelong learning and approved in accordance with Prague communication. The main printship is the filling of the workload, taking into account the characteristics of the work, the composition of the program, and finally the control of the training results at this level. This is in no way alien to the original idea of ECTS as a credit transfer system. The idea of recognizing ECTS credits abroad was primarily a planned experimental scheme based on the characteristics of this level, as well as the curriculum and the prior agreements of the faculty on the teaching load. Of course, credit units: they require not only to determine the educational burden that corresponds to the ECTS unit and to describe the appropriate amount of credits, but also the content, methodology, methods of knowledge management of the program proposed by the university, as well as the conditions for supporting foreign students.

A relatively simple but significant feature of ECTS is the control of knowledge: debts are not a factor of control, but always indicate the full performance of the student as part of the curriculum. Thus, in the credit collection system, credit units are collected within the framework of a consistent training program that reflects a certain amount of work that has been performed to a certain extent successfully for a well-known qualification.

There is one side to using ECTS as the main tool in reforming the education system, this is due to the fact that the curriculum of the faculties is often excessive and deprives the students of the opportunity to study on time.

It is possible to agree that ECTS credit can be used to accumulate credits without the need to modify or adjust the basic elements of the system. In fact, the plans to adapt this system are gradually taking the form that corresponds to the idea of "collecting credits for Lifelong Learning", which was supported by the ministers of education in Bologna and Prague.

In general, students have a positive opinion about the accumulation of loans. Nearly three-quarters of the student associations believe that this system has a great advantage in creating more flexible individual curricula. The number of overloaded training programs is reduced and a clear sequence is carried out between the training programs within the universities. Only a fifth of the student associations surveyed said the benefits of collecting loans would remain unknown to them.

In some countries, ECTS savings is the usual standard system: in Germany (52%), in France (56%), in Greece (60%), in Austria (66%), in Ireland (80%), in Switzerland and Norvegia (about 86%). Romania (93%) and Denmark (96) / other countries are very advanced in the matter of

national savings systems, for example, Sweden (60%), Great Britain (63,6%), Turkey (68,4%), Finland (81, 5%) and Estonia (85,7%).

It seems surprising that almost three quarters of European universities are already using the credit collection system, especially for ECTS consultants who are familiar with the process of introducing ECTS and other credit systems. These results clearly show that EHEA with the ECTS system is one of the main tools for creating a European educational space.

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